

POTENTIAL OF PLANT EXTRACTS ON HISTOLOGICAL REGENERATION OF MALNOURISHED RAT SKIN

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Skin is the organ that wraps the entire outer surface of the body and is the largest and heaviest organ of the entire body (Tortora and Derrickson, 2009). The skin serves to protect the body from external influences. Skin tissue consists of millions of cells that can experience death and replace with new cells that will grow (Akbar, 2007). The skin consists of 2 main layers, namely the epidermis and dermis. The epidermis is a layer of epithelial tissue derived from the ectoderm layer, while the dermis is a rather dense connective tissue derived from the mesoderm. Underneath there is a layer of loose connective tissue, the hypodermis, which in some places consists of fatty tissue (Kalangi, 2013). Damage to skin histology can occur by several causes including aging, physical trauma such as cuts, scratches, infections, external exposure, malnutrition, and others. Until now, research on skin histopathology repair has mostly examined wound healing, infection or damage caused by physical trauma. However, research on skin histopathology repair due to malnutrition is still minimal. In addition, the use of natural materials such as plant extracts is also minimally used as an agent for histopathological regeneration of skin due to malnutrition. Indonesia has an abundance of flora with a myriad of benefits which is a great opportunity for researchers to develop various kinds of drugs in research on histology regeneration of body tissues that are damaged both from inside and outside the body. One of the plants that has a wide distribution and has not been widely used is Paga Bean (*Phaseolus Lunatus* L). This plant can be used as a regenerating agent for skin histology damaged by malnutrition because its content can improve nutrition, improving the histology structure of skin damaged by malnutrition.

Many types of bioactive compounds, macronutrients and micronutrients are contained in various plants that have the potential as agents of skin histology regeneration. Bioactive compounds in these plants have antiinflammatory, antifungal, antibacterial, analgesic effects and can increase antioxidant activity that can stimulate tissue healing. Several previous studies have used several plant extracts for skin tissue repair including the potential of *Strobilanthes crispus* leaf extract for wound healing in mice (Al-Henhena *et al.*, 2011), the potential of *licorice* extract for wound healing (Assar *et al.*, 2021), *Quercus brantii* extract as a skin wound healing agent (Zangeneh *et al.*, 2019), clove extract (*Eugenol*) for wound healing (Ashjazadeh *et al.*, 2019), *Scrophularia striata* extract in wound healing (Ghashghaii *et al.*, 2017), *Stevia rebaudia* extract for wound healing (Das, 2013), *Elaeis guineensis* extract for wound healing of albino mouse model (Sasidharan *et al.*, 2010), *Atropa belladonna* L extract for skin wound healing (Gál *et al.*, 2009), *Portulaca pilosa* extract in wound healing of wistar rats (Barros *et al.*, 2017), *Nerium oleander* and *Aloe vera* extracts in wound healing (Akgun *et al.*, 2017), *Parkia biglobosa* extract in open wound healing (Builders *et al.*, 2019), *Vitis labrusca* extract for wound healing (Santos *et al.*, 2021), *Kalanchoe pinnata* extract for wound healing (Nayak *et al.*, 2010), effect of Saudi pomegranate peels extract on excision wound of diabetic rats (Karim *et al.*, 2021), effect of *Centella asiatica* extract on wound healing (Ermertcan *et al.*, 2008), effect of *Liquorice* root extract on dermal wound (Oloumi *et al.*, 2007), the effect of *Cynara umilis* extract on dermal burn healing (Salhi *et al.*, 2023), the effect of *Punica granatum* L extract on dermal wound healing (Hayouni *et al.*, 2011), the effect of *Lonicera japonica* leaf extract on excision wound healing (Chen *et al.*, 2012), the effect of gambier plant on wound healing (Sumosa *et al.*, 2014), as

well as the effect of *Boesenbergia rotunda* rhizome extract for rat wound healing (Mahmood *et al.*, 2010) show that the compounds and ingredients contained in plants have been widely used in research on improving skin histology due to physical trauma, especially due to incision wounds and burns.

Previous studies have shown that there has been a lot of research related to the regeneration of body tissue histology, especially skin, using various kinds of plant extracts. In terms of the use of animal models, the most widely used is due to incision wounds and burns, while skin tissue damage due to malnutrition is still minimally used. Malnutrition is a condition of individual failure to meet nutritional needs, reduced (malnutrition) or excessive (overnutrition) food intake, or non-specific changes in nutritional status due to disease or treatment. Sakya *et al.*, (2016) defined malnutrition as a condition where the body does not get enough nutrients from a lack of intake of nutrients from the food consumed. Malnutrition has a significant effect on skin tissue, impacting structure, function and overall health. Inadequate protein nutrition can lead to wound healing retardation and bedsore damage (Mathus-Vliegen, 2004). According to Leite *et al* (2011), malnutrition leads to thinner dermis and epidermis, and a reduced percentage of collagen in the skin. This leads to weakened skin structure and decreased skin trophism, making it more susceptible to damage and slower to heal.

From the methods carried out, the administration of extracts is done in-vivo by direct injection into rats. Providing plant nutrients in animal feed is still minimal to improve the histological structure of body tissues due to malnutrition. Lima beans or paga beans are a type of legume that has been widely used in various studies on malnutrition. However, research that focuses on skin histology regeneration due to malnutrition using paga bean plants has not been studied even though paga beans have enormous potential in repairing body tissue histology. Research on the effectiveness of Paga bean on the improvement of body tissue histology that has been carried out is the effect of Paga bean on brain histology and its effect on cognitive function. Based on research by Maliza *et al* (2023), feeding paga bean meal can improve growth, especially through increased body weight and prevent brain degeneration due to chronic malnutrition. In addition, paga bean flour also acts as a source of complex nutrients that protect against systemic malnutrition in various organ systems, including the brain. Rats fed a diet with 12% protein content for six weeks showed significant changes in body weight, proportion of degenerated cells, and histopathological features in the cerebral cortex and hippocampus compared to a normal group fed a diet with 20% protein content for six weeks. These changes also affected the cognitive function of rats that received a low-protein diet (Maliza *et al.*, 2024). Therefore, further research is needed on the effect of paga bean on skin histology regeneration. The potential of paga beans is great in overcoming malnutrition, which affects changes in organ tissue histology.

Research on malnutrition is necessary to reduce stunting cases in Indonesia. This is because malnutrition has a massive impact on damage to other organs including the skin. Fulfillment of nutrition for the lower class of society is a problem because they cannot afford to buy basic ingredients with high prices such as meat. Therefore, research on natural ingredients that are cheap and rich in nutrients must always be developed so that the problem of malnutrition can be resolved even among the lower classes. Paga bean is a suitable candidate as an agent in overcoming malnutrition due to its high amino acid content. With such high nutritional value, the development of histology regeneration research must also be developed, one of which is skin histology. The very important role of skin also encourages research on this subject to be of more attention. This shows the novelty of research in the regeneration of skin histology damage using the plants used, the method of administration of plant extracts, and the regeneration of skin histopathology due to malnutrition.

REFERENCES

- Akbar, A. (2007). *Anatomi & Fisiologi Kulit Wajah*. Jakarta: PT Elex Media Komputindo. 16-17
- Akgun, S. G., Aydemir, S., Ozkan, N., Yuksel, M., & Sardas, S. (2017). Evaluation Of The Wound Healing Potential Of Aloe Vera-based Extract Of Nerium Oleander. *North Clin Istanb*, 4(3), 205-212.
- Al-Henhena, N., Mahmood, A. A., Al-Magrami, A., Nor Syuhada, A. B., Zahra, A. A., Summaya, M. D., ... & Salmah, I. (2011). Histological Study Of Wound Healing Potential By Ethanol Leaf Extract Of Strobilanthes Crispus In Rats. *J Med Plants Res*, 5(16), 3666-3669.
- Ashjzadeh, M. A., Jahandideh, A., Abedi, G., Akbarzadeh, A., & Hesarak, S. (2019). Histopathology And Histomorphological Study Of Wound Healing Using Clove Extract Nanofibers (Eugenol) Compared To Zinc Oxide Nanofibers On The Skin Of Rats. *Archives of Razi Institute*, 74(3), 267-277.
- Assar, D. H., Elhabashi, N., Mokhbatly, A. A. A., Ragab, A. E., Elbially, Z. I., Rizk, S. A., ... & Atiba, A. (2021). Wound Healing Potential Of Licorice Extract In Rat Model: Antioxidants, Histopathological, Immunohistochemical And Gene Expression Evidences. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 143, 112151.
- Barros, A. S. A., Carvalho, H. O., Dos Santos, I. V. F., Taglialegra, T., dos Santos Sampaio, T. I., Duarte, J. L., ... & Carvalho, J. C. T. (2017). Study Of The Non-clinical Healing Activities Of The Extract And Gel Of Portulaca Pilosa L. In Skin Wounds In Wistar Rats: A Preliminary Study. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 96, 182-190.
- Builders, M. I., Joseph, O. S., & Vhrithere, A. R. (2019). Effect Of Parkia Biglobosa Extract On Open Skin Wound Healing In Dexamethasone-induced Hyperglycaemia And Histological Assessment In Rats. *African Journal Of Pharmacy And Pharmacology (Ajpp)*, 13 (8).
- Chen, W. C., Liou, S. S., Tzeng, T. F., Lee, S. L., & Liu, I. M. (2012). Wound Repair And Anti-inflammatory Potential Of Lonicera Japonica In Excision Wound-induced Rats. *BMC Complementary And Alternative Medicine*, 12, 1-9.
- Das, K. (2013). Wound Healing Potential Of Aqueous Crude Extract Of Stevia Rebaudiana In Mice. *Revista Brasileira de Farmacognosia*, 23, 351-357.
- Ermertcan, A. T., Inan, S., Ozturkcan, S., Bilac, C., & Cilaker, S. (2008). Comparison Of The Effects Of Collagenase And Extract Of Centella Asiatica In An Experimental Model Of Wound Healing: An Immunohistochemical And Histopathological Study. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*, 16(5), 674-681.
- Gál, P., Toporcer, T., Grendel, T., Vidová, Z., Smetana Jr, K., Dvořánková, B., ... & Bačkor, M. (2009). Effect Of Atropa Belladonna L. On Skin Wound Healing: Biomechanical And Histological Study In Rats And In Vitro Study In Keratinocytes, 3T3 Fibroblasts, And Human Umbilical Vein Endothelial Cells. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*, 17(3), 378-386.
- Ghashghaii, A., Hashemnia, M., Nikousefat, Z., Zangeneh, M. M., & Zangeneh, A. (2017). Wound Healing Potential Of Methanolic Extract Of Scrophularia Striata In Rats. *Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 23(4), 256-263.
- Hayouni, E. A., Miled, K., Boubaker, S., Bellasfar, Z., Abedrabba, M., Iwaski, H., ... & Hamdi, M. (2011). Hydroalcoholic Extract Based-ointment From Punica Granatum L. Peels With Enhanced In Vivo Healing Potential On Dermal Wounds. *Phytomedicine: International Journal of Phytotherapy & Phytopharmacology*, 18(11), 976-985.
- Kalangi, S. J. (2013). Histofisiologi kulit. *Jurnal Biomedik: JBM*, 5(3).

- Karim, S., Alkreathy, H. M., Ahmad, A., & Khan, M. I. (2021). Effects Of Methanolic Extract Based-gel From Saudi Pomegranate Peels With Enhanced Healing Potential On Excision Wounds In Diabetic Rats. *Frontiers In Pharmacology*, 12, 704503.
- Leite, S., Júnior, A., Andrade, T., Masson, D., & Frade, M. (2011). Experimental Models Of Malnutrition And Its Effect On Skin Trophism.. *Anais Brasileiros De Dermatologia*, 86(4), 681-8
- Mahmood, A. A., Mariod, A. A., Abdelwahab, S. I., Ismail, S., & Al-Bayat, F. (2010). Potential Activity Of Ethanolic Extract Of Boesenbergia Rotunda (L.) Rhizomes Extract In Accelerating Wound Healing In Rats. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 4(15), 1570-1576.
- Maliza, Rita, Tofrizal, A., Santoso, P., Jannatan, R., & Amatu Zikrah, A. (2023). Effects Of Lima Bean (Phaseolus Lunatus) Flour On Cognitive Function And Growth Recovery Malnutrition Rats. *Journal of Microbiology, Biotechnology and Food Sciences*, 13(4), e10332. <https://doi.org/10.55251/jmbfs.10332>**
- Maliza, Rita., Allimuddin, Tofrizal., Fadillah. (2024). Effect of Low Protein Diet Treatment for Six Weeks on The Brain Histopathological and Cognitive Function in The Wistar Rat. *Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 44(1)**
- Mathus-Vliegen, E. M. 2004. Old Age, Malnutrition, And Pressure Sores: An Ill-fated Alliance. *J. Gerontol. A Biol. Sci. Med. Sci.* 59: 355–360
- Nayak, B. S., Marshall, J. R., & Isitor, G. (2010). Wound Healing Potential Of Ethanolic Extract Of Kalanchoe Pinnata Lam. Leaf—a Preliminary Study. *CSIR*, 48(6)
- Oloumi, Mohammad Mahdi, Derakhshanfar, A., & Nikpour, A.. (2007). Healing Potential Of Liquorice Root Extract On Dermal Wounds In Rats. *Journal Of Veterinary Research*, 62(4), 147-154. DOI: <https://sid.ir/paper/35058/en>
- Sakya, A. T. (2016). Peningkatan Ketersediaan Nutrisi Mikro Pada Tanaman: Upayamengurangi Malnutrisi Pada Manusia. *Caraka Tani: Journal of Sustainable Agriculture*, 31(2), 118-128.
- Salhi, N., El Guourami, O., Rouas, L., Moussaid, S., Moutawalli, A., Benkhoulil, F. Z., ... & Cherrah, Y. (2023). Evaluation Of The Wound Healing Potential Of Cynara Humilis Extracts In The Treatment Of Skin Burns. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2023(1), 5855948.
- Santos, T. S., Santos, I. D. D., Pereira-Filho, R. N., Gomes, S. V., Lima-Verde, I. B., Marques, M. N., ... & Albuquerque-Júnior, R. L. D. (2021). Histological Evidence Of Wound Healing Improvement In Rats Treated With Oral Administration Of Hydroalcoholic Extract Of Vitis Labrusca. *Current Issues In Molecular Biology*, 43(1), 335-352.
- Sasidharan, S., Nilawatyi, R., Xavier, R., Latha, L. Y., & Amala, R. (2010). Wound Healing Potential Of Elaeis Guineensis Jacqleaves In An Infected Albino Rat Model. *Molecules*, 15(5), 3186-3199.
- Sumosa, N. S., Efrizal., Resti, Rahayu. (2014). Pengaruh Gambir (Uncaria gambir R.) Terhadap Penyembuhan Luka Bakar Pada Mencit Putih (Mus musculus L.) Jantan. *Jurnal Biologi Universitas Andalas*, 3(4): 283-2**
- Tortora, G. J dan B. Derrickson. (2009). *Principles of Anatomy and Physiology*. United States of America: John Wiley and Sons Inc. 123.
- Zangeneh, M. M., Pooyanmehr, M., & Zangeneh, A. (2019). Biochemical, Histopathological, And Pharmacological Evaluations Of Cutaneous Wound Healing Properties Of Quercus Brantii Ethanolic Extract Ointment In Male Rats. *Comparative clinical pathology*, 28, 1483-1493.